

Plastic Pirates in Nova Scotia – Litter pollution results for fall 2024

Information for photos on title page

Top: School students from Cunard Junior High after their sampling activity at Williams Lake.

Middle left: Litter sorting in progress by students from Rockingstone Heights School at Kidston Lake

Middle centre: Litter collected by students from Beechville-Lakeside-Timberlea at Half Mile Lake

Middle right: Large amounts of litter collected by students from Shannon Park School

Bottom left: Data recording by a student from Crichton Park School at Lake Banook

Bottom right: Students from Leslie Thomas Junior High with their sorting station at First Lake

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Dear school students, dear teachers, dear volunteers and participants,

the pollution of our ocean, lakes and rivers has become a global environmental problem. Plastic pollution is a serious threat for many animals but it also affects us as humans. Especially problematic are single-use plastics. These are items made entirely or partially of plastic (for example coffee-to-go cups and cigarette butts), that are disposed off after being used only once. Many people all across the globe get active on plastic pollution, for example by collecting valuable scientific data about this problem. This in turn helps to identify the scale of the problem and provides necessary information for solutions. You have been actively involved in such a research program, called the Plastic Pirates. You have measured and established sampling areas, collected and classified litter, and recorded your data. Your data was uploaded to the website of the Plastic Pirates (<https://www.plastic-pirates.eu/en/results/map>) and we, as the coordinators of this program here in Nova Scotia, have written this short report, which presents the findings of all participants. You can show this report to anyone who is interested. And you can also see all the original data you collected in the data table attached to this report (you can find it on zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14507148>). Thank you so much for participating! Because of your involvement we now know a little more about litter pollution in Nova Scotia.

Halifax, 23rd of January 2025

Tim Kiessling, Maya Goldchtaub, and Tony R. Walker

Your participation

During the months of October and November 2024 a total of nine organisations participated in the Plastic Pirates program in Nova Scotia. Among the 275 participants were 221 school students and 54 teachers, chaperones, volunteers and coordinators (you can see the organisations and number of participants in Table 1). Overall, we have sampled six different lakes and two sites at the ocean (Table 1). We estimated that a combined 635 hours were spent conducting the samplings.

Table 1. List of participating organisations, number of participants, sampling date and locations.

Name of organisation	Number of participants	Sampling date	Sampling location
Cunard Junior High	27	2024-10-10	Williams Lake
Beechville Lakeside Timberlea Elementary	22	2024-10-16	Half Mile Lake
Rockingstone Heights	47	2024-10-30	Kidston Lake
Leslie Thomas Junior High	36	2024-11-05	First Lake
Cavalier Drive School	48	2024-11-06	First Lake
Dalhousie University – Let’s Talk Science	4	2024-11-12	Chocolate Lake
Crichton Park School	29	2024-11-14	Lake Banook
École Shannon Park School	54	2024-11-15	The Narrows, Atlantic Ocean
St. Margaret's Bay Stewardship Association	8	2024-11-16	Atlantic Ocean (not identified due to nature conservation)

Results for litter densities

The goal of this activity was to find out how much litter was present in a specific area. This allows us to compare our result to other sampling sites across the world. During this activity litter was collected only in specific squares. The length of each square was 3 meters, so that each square had 9 square meters (m²). The squares were established at three defined locations: very close to the water, towards the upper end of the shore, and in between those two locations. Some groups investigated more squares than other groups but all groups investigated at least three squares. In total 75 sampling squares were investigated, which sums up to represent 675 m². Almost all groups found between 0.1 and 0.8 litter items per 1 m² but the group investigating squares at The Narrows found 6.6 litter items per 1 m² (you can compare the results between the sites in Figure 1)! For comparison, at rivers in Germany 0.8 litter items were found per 1 m² (this was shown by Dittmann and colleagues, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2024.117253>).

Figure 1: Litter items per 1 m² at different sampling locations investigated by the Plastic Pirates in Nova Scotia.

Results for litter composition

The goal of this activity was to find out which litter items occur most frequently and to assess whether problematic single-use plastics are found often. During this activity as much litter as possible was collected within a certain time, usually between 20 and 40 minutes. Afterwards the litter was sorted according to specific categories. Overall more than 3,000 litter items were collected and categorized by participants in this group. Most litter items were categorized as “Other plastics”, followed by plastic wrappers and cigarette butts (you can see the added-up data from all groups in Table 2 and also in the data table attached to this report). When looking at broader categories, almost half of the items (48%) found were single-use plastics, followed by plastics other than single-use items. All the other broader categories such as glass, metal, paper and other items were found less often (you can compare this when looking at Figure 2). Overall 114 kilograms of litter were removed from the environment during this activity. For comparison, data collected by school students at rivers in Germany showed that cigarette butts, glass shards and plastic wrappers were found most frequently there. Also, very similar to data collected in Nova Scotia, 44% of items were single-use plastics (see the study by Kiessling and colleagues, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2023.03.042>).

Table 2: Litter items found per different categories at sampling locations investigated by the Plastic Pirates in Nova Scotia. Single-use plastic items are highlighted in grey.

Litter item	Count	Proportion
Other plastic items	603	20%
Plastic snack packaging and wrappers	585	19%
Cigarette butts	282	9%
Plastic bags	197	6%
Paper	175	6%
Other litter items	159	5%
Polystyrene pieces	150	5%
Glass shards	144	5%
Plastic take away and fast food packaging, including coffee to go cups and lids	128	4%
Plastic lids for beverage bottles	105	3%
Plastic beverage bottles	101	3%
Metal beverage cans	89	3%
Aluminium foil	49	2%
Other metal items	44	1%
Textiles	41	1%
Rubber	40	1%
Hygiene articles consisting of plastic	37	1%
Small pieces of plastic	35	1%
Plastic cutlery and plates, including straws	30	1%
Glass bottles for beverages	14	0%
Metal bottle caps for beverages	13	0%
Balloons	8	0%
Other glass items	2	0%
Cotton buds with plastic rod	1	0%
Total single-use plastic items (grey categories above)	1466	48%
Total of all litter items	3032	100%

Figure 2: Broad categories of litter items found during the sampling activity of the Plastic Pirates in Nova Scotia and after classifying more than 3,000 litter items.

Summary

The data collected shows that litter can be found everywhere and that some sites might be especially polluted, such as the ocean sampling site at The Narrows. Single-use plastics are a big part of the problem, making up almost half of the litter found. Many plastic wrappers and cigarette butts have been found, which is concerning. Cigarette butts can pollute a lot of water because of the toxins contained in the filter material. The data also suggests that visitors of lakes are the main source of pollution, leaving single-use plastics behind. The situation at the ocean is a little different. Here illegal garbage dumps were important litter sources as well as fishing debris and remains of polystyrene. In the future it would be very interesting to repeat the sampling in the spring to compare litter quantities between seasons. Also, sampling more sites at the ocean would be interesting.

Thank you!

Thanks to you and your school class and volunteer organisation we know a little more about the litter pollution at lakes and the ocean in Nova Scotia! With this you have also contributed to finding a solution to the plastic pollution problem. Without your support this study would not have been possible! Specifically, we would like to acknowledge the contribution of the following teachers, chaperones and volunteers as well as the many anonymous school students and further volunteers who have participated in the initiative: Alexia Bulger, Angela Akpan, Angela Gillis, Beverly Anthony, Bria Woods, Claire McKenzie, Crystal Isert, Débora Boratto, Elizabeth Cousineau, Emma-Joy Swan, Erin Delaney, Fiyinfolu Onososen, Hailey Meade, Jasmine Figg, Jenna DeWolfe, Jennifer Blackburn, Kathy Laprise, Laura Washburn, Laurel Schut, Mary-Emma Murphy, Mike Lancaster, Neil Daigle, Nicole Saulnier, Parisana Low, Sarah Thorpe, Shree Gokul, and Tara MacDonald. We are also grateful to Janto Schönberg, Sinja Dittmann, Mandy Hinzmann, Doris Knoblauch and Katrin Knickmeier, who have supported this project from Germany. The following organisations helped to make this project a reality by funding research material, transport costs, and – most importantly – our work: Let's Talk Science at Dalhousie University, Kiel University ("Zukunftsvertrag Studium und Lehre stärken"), the Ocean Frontier Institute (Visiting Fellowship Program 2024, through an award from the Canada First Research Excellence Fund to Tim Kiessling), and the School for Resource and Environmental Studies at Dalhousie University. Funding support was also provided from the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC), Grant/Award Number RGPIN-2018-04119 awarded to Tony R. Walker.

About the Plastic Pirates

The Plastic Pirates are a citizen science initiative founded in 2016 by Kiel Science Factory in Germany (<https://www.forschungs-werkstatt.de/en/>) and the Científicos de la Basura in Chile (<https://cientificosdelabasura.ucn.cl/>). Since 2018 the Ecologic Institute in Germany (<https://www.ecologic.eu/>) has been part of the Plastic Pirates. In recent years, the initiative has been expanded to further European countries (<https://www.plastic-pirates.eu/en>). In Nova Scotia the Plastic Pirates program is coordinated as a cooperation between the Plastic Pirates in Germany and Let's Talk Science (<https://letstalkscience.ca/outreach/dalhousie>) and the School for Resource and Environmental Studies, both located at Dalhousie University (<https://www.dal.ca/faculty/science/sres.html>). More than 25,000 school students have been participating in the program in Germany so far and the participants have contributed substantially to our understanding of plastic pollution in rivers.

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This report as well as the research data collected by the school students and volunteers is available at zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14507148>. The report is published under Creative Commons license CC BY 4.0.

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